

Submitted as *Short Communication* to the Journal of the European Ceramic Society; Submitted Nov. 2013; Revised February 2014.

Sliding-wear resistance of liquid-phase-sintered SiC containing graphite nanodispersoids

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Abstract

The influence was investigated of a graphite nanodispersoid addition on the lubricated sliding-wear behaviour of liquid-phase-sintered (LPS) SiC ceramics fabricated by spark-plasma sintering (SPS). The graphite nanodispersoids, introduced into the microstructure of the LPS SiC ceramic to act as self-lubricating phase, were obtained by graphitization of diamond nanoparticles during the SPS. It was found that the graphite nanodispersoid addition results in a lower resistance to mild wear, attributable to the lower hardness of graphite and the null lubrication it provides. Moreover, the graphite nanodispersoids, which mostly locate at grain boundaries/faces, worsen the cohesion of SiC grains, contributing together with the higher mild-wear rate to an early transition to the severe-wear stage. On the contrary, the graphite

nanodispersoids were effective at improving the resistance to severe wear because they increase the fracture toughness while providing some external lubrication. Relevant implications for the microstructural design of advanced triboceramics are discussed.

Keywords: SiC; wear; microstructure; spark-plasma sintering

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1. Introduction

Wear of polycrystalline ceramics subjected to prolonged sliding contact is typically a two-step process, with an initial, deformation-controlled mild wear, followed by a transition to subsequent, fracture-controlled wear [1-11]. Fracture of grain boundaries leads inevitably to severe wear by grain pull-out at the surface and subsurface, with attendant loss of structural integrity. The safest use of materials thus requires that the severe-wear regime be avoided, or at least delayed as much as possible so that the triboceramic indeed operates within the mild-wear regime (i.e., the safe-life approach). If utilization under severe wear is inevitable, then it is critical to minimize the wear damage and rate (i.e., the fail-safe approach). Whichever the case may be, microstructural engineering has proved to be an effective strategy with which to improve the sliding-wear resistance of polycrystalline structural ceramics. In particular, current guidelines to control the wear in the case of the typical equiaxed-grain microstructures, without using surface-modification treatments, include increasing (i) the hardness [9,11], (ii) the grain-boundary toughness [3,11], and (iii) the compressive surface stresses [4], as well as reducing (i) the grain size [1-3,6,8], (ii) the amount of softer intergranular phases [6], and (iii) internal tensile residual stresses [6], approaches which can be used alone or in combination if possible.

The use of internal lubricants (i.e., low friction phases homogeneously dispersed in the microstructure) has also been considered [12,13]. This strategy is particularly attractive in open systems, where external lubrication is not possible. Not surprisingly, flaky particles of hexagonal graphite and BN, two classic lamellar solids with low friction coefficient, have been used to induce self-lubrication in ceramics. But their problem is that, unless textured with their largest surface parallel to the contact, flaky particles are not effective at decreasing the friction during mild wear because the area exposed to sliding is relatively small. On the contrary, the modest

hardness of these low-friction phases results in a higher rate of deformation-controlled mild wear, and in turn in early transitions to severe wear. While texturing is in principle possible by (uniaxial) pressure-assisted sintering [12], in practice accommodation of the soft internal lubricant flakes often takes place, which hinders preferential alignment [13]. Flaky particles are, however, effective at inducing external lubrication in the severe-wear regime [13], once they have undergone pull-out from the microstructure.

Based on the above, in the present proof-of-concept study we investigate the use of equiaxed nanoparticles, rather than flaky coarse particles, as internal lubricant phase. As a model system, we prepared by spark plasma sintering (SPS) a liquid-phase-sintered (LPS) SiC ceramic containing graphite nanodispersoids, and compared its sliding-wear resistance with that of a reference LPS SiC ceramic without internal lubricants. Ultimately, the aim is to extract additional guidelines for the microstructural design of highly wear-resistant polycrystalline ceramics for engineering applications.

2. Experimental Procedure

The LPS SiC ceramics without and with graphite nanodispersoids (hereafter denoted simply as SiC-Ref and SiC-nG, respectively) were obtained by SPS of SiC+Y₃Al₅O₁₂ and SiC+Y₃Al₅O₁₂+nano-diamond powder mixtures (SiC:Y₃Al₅O₁₂ weight ratio of 9:1 in both cases, and 10 wt.% nano-diamond loading in the latter), respectively. The methods of aqueous-colloidal processing and microstructural features of the powders have been described elsewhere [14]. Nano-diamond was deliberately used as precursor of the graphite equiaxed nanodispersoids because its in-situ graphitization during SPS will readily result in an LPS SiC/nano-graphite composite with the desired microstructural architecture. This contrasts with other graphite

sources (i.e., nano-graphite and carbon black), which are expected to evolve towards an equilibrium, flaky morphology [12]. SPS was performed (SPS-510CE, SPS Syntex Inc., Japan) in graphite dies at 1800 °C (heating ramp 200 °C·min⁻¹) for 5 min under 100 MPa, in vacuum. The rapid SPS cycle is to ensure the densification by liquid-phase sintering with hardly any growth of the graphite nanodispersoids.

The sintered specimens were diamond polished to a 1- μ m finish using routine ceramographic methods and were also broken. Their microstructures were subsequently characterized by scanning electron microscopy at 15 kV accelerating voltage with secondary electrons (SEM; Quanta 3D FEG, FEI, The Netherlands), and by X-ray diffractometry with monochromatic Cu-K α_1 radiation (XRD; D8 Advance, Bruker AXS, Germany). The mechanical properties were examined by Vickers-indentation tests (MV-1, Matsuzawa, Tokyo, Japan) at 98 N in order to determine the hardness (H_V) and toughness (K_{IC}) through standard formulae [15,16]. Sliding-wear tests were conducted in a tribometer (Falex multi-specimen, Faville-Le Vally Corp., USA) configured in the ball-on-three-disks geometry [1,6], using a commercially-available bearing-grade Si₃N₄ ball (NBD 200, Cerbec, USA) of radius 6.35 mm, regular diesel fuel as lubricant (viscosity of ~ 3.8 cSt), normal contact load of 130 N, and rotation speed of 25 rpm. The average diameter of the circular wear scars as a function of time, measured under the optical microscope (two orthogonal measurements per disk, 3 disks per material), was used in order to quantify the extent of wear damage. Finally, the wear damage at the microstructural level was observed by SEM.

3. Results

Fig. 1 shows representative SEM micrographs at intermediate magnification of the fracture surfaces of SiC-Ref and SiC-nG, which broke intergranularly. It can be seen that the two materials are fully dense, and comprise equiaxed SiC grains, which are somewhat smaller and more uniform in size in SiC-nG. In particular, the average SiC grain size measured from SEM images taken on polished surfaces, like those shown in Fig. 2, is $\sim 0.7 \mu\text{m}$ in SiC-Ref and $\sim 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ in SiC-nG. Furthermore, while the grain size in SiC-nG is relatively homogeneous, there is a larger size dispersion in SiC-Ref (with small grains and grains as large as $2 \mu\text{m}$). Also, SiC-Ref contains grain boundaries that are typical of LPS SiC ceramics (see Fig. 1A inset), whilst SiC-nG exhibits a one-dimensional mat of nanoparticles on the faces of the SiC grains (see Fig. 1B inset), in addition to the expected oxide secondary phase. The nanoparticles are homogeneously spread across the microstructure, and have uniform sizes in the 20-50 nm range and equiaxed shapes. The XRD pattern of SiC-nG shown in Fig. 3 exhibits, apart from α -SiC (SiC grains) and $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (secondary phase) peaks, broad graphite peaks, thus confirming the sought graphitization of nano-diamond during SPS. Assuming a complete diamond-to-graphite transformation, SiC-nG has the composition 79.6 vol.% SiC + 6.2 vol.% $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ + 14.2 vol.% graphite. As expected, the XRD pattern of SiC-Ref only displayed α -SiC and $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ peaks, and thus SiC-Ref has the composition 92.8 vol.% SiC + 7.2 vol.% $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$.

The slightly smaller and more uniform grain size of SiC-nG reflects that the diamond nanoparticles, or graphite nanoparticles after graphitization, influenced the rapid liquid-phase sintering of SiC, which is explained as follows [17,18]. First, the diamond/graphite nanodeposits and adhered nanoclusters interfere during the interfacial dissolution and reprecipitation steps. Second, the nanoclusters, adhered or isolated, are obstacles to the diffusion of the Si and C

atoms. And third, the addition of nano-diamond reduces the SiC volume fraction (from 92.8 to 79.6 vol.%). These three effects reinforce each other in slowing down the growth of the SiC grains by Ostwald ripening (where the larger grains grow at the expense of the smaller ones), as observed experimentally.

In regards to the mechanical properties, the hardness values measured by Vickers indentation were 25.1 ± 0.7 and 12.9 ± 0.9 GPa for SiC-Ref and SiC-nG, respectively. Given that the SiC-nG indeed contains a lower amount of $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ secondary phase (i.e., 6.2 vs 7.2 vol.%) and are dense, the lower hardness of SiC-nG is due to the presence of the very soft graphite particles in its microstructure, and to the greater weakness of its interfaces (i.e., poorer grain cohesion [12]) which enhances interfacial shear faulting. On the contrary, SiC-nG is tougher than SiC-Ref: 4.3 ± 0.5 vs 2.9 ± 0.2 MPam^{1/2}, respectively. Given that the fracture mode is essentially of intergranular type in both cases (see Fig. 1) and that SiC-nG has a smaller grain size, the greater toughness of SiC-nG is attributable essentially to the dissipation of crack energy ahead of the tip by deformation of the softer graphite particles [15].

Fig. 4 shows the sliding-wear curves of SiC-Ref and SiC-nG, which both have the typical shape reported for other polycrystalline ceramics. In particular, there is a first stage with relatively low damage (termed mild wear), followed by a transition, at a given sliding time, to a second stage with much greater damage (termed severe wear). It can however be observed that SiC-nG is less resistant than SiC-Ref to the mild wear in exhibiting a greater extent of damage (i.e., wear-scar diameter) and wear rate (115 vs 80 $\mu\text{m}/\log(t)$, respectively). Moreover, SiC-nG enters the severe-wear stage 12 times earlier than SiC-Ref: transition times of 25 and 250 min, respectively. In the severe-wear regime the trend reverses, with SiC-nG showing a lower wear rate than SiC-Ref (187 vs 310 $\mu\text{m}/\log(t)$). For the limited sliding times investigated here (i.e., not

more than 500 min), the extent of damage is always higher in SiC-nG. However, it is reasonable to infer from the extrapolation of the curves that for much longer sliding times the accumulated wear damage in SiC-nG, most likely, will be eventually lower than in SiC-Ref, as a result of its lower severe-wear rate.

In the mild-wear regime, the friction coefficient measured in both SiC-Ref and SiC-nG is the same: 0.15-0.16. However, differences appear in the severe-wear regime, with values of 0.25 and 0.19 being measured for SiC-Ref and SiC-nG, respectively. These are the same trends observed earlier in LPS SiC ceramics with flaky BN addition [13]. The non-occurrence of self-lubrication during mild wear is attributable to the relatively low area of graphite exposed directly to contact, because most of the graphite nanodispersoids are indeed trapped between grain faces. However, the lower friction during the severe wear is due to the lubrication provided by the abundant graphite nanodispersoids homogeneously spread as third bodies under the contact after grain pull-out has taken place.

Fig. 5 shows details of the damage at the end of the wear tests at both the macroscopic and the microstructural scales. Apart from the surface scratches characteristic of plastic damage, larger pits produced by grain pull-out from the surface and sub-surface are clearly observed both in SiC-Ref and in SiC-nG. This reflects the occurrence of mild wear followed by severe wear. Also, the comparison between the SEM micrographs indicates that the extent of damage (i.e., both wear scar diameter and magnitude of the material removal) is doubtless greater in SiC-nG, which agrees well with the wear curves in Fig. 4.

4. Discussion

It is instructive to analyze the sliding-wear data in Fig. 4 in terms of simple fracture mechanics. The principle is that during the mild-wear stage, plastic deformation (in the form of dislocation pile-ups introduced by the combination of normal and lateral forces in the sliding contact) accumulates within the grains of the different phases as a function of sliding time (t). This induces increasing tensile stresses ($\sigma_D(t)$) on pre-existing defects. The time-dependent stress intensity factor ($K(t)$) acting on the flaws may then be written as [1,6]:

$$K(t) = \psi(\sigma_D(t) + q) \cdot \beta \cdot D^{0.5}$$

where D is the average grain size, q is the constant residual stress generated during the processing itself due to the thermal expansion mismatch between the different phases, and the constants ψ and $\beta (\leq 1)$ are geometrical and scaling factors, respectively. Like a fatigue effect, at a certain critical t (t_c), $K(t)$ reaches the critical value of the grain-boundary toughness ($K(t_c) = K^{GB}$), thus marking the onset of the severe-wear stage. Coalescence of propagating cracks leads to material removal by grain pull-out, thus increasing notably the wear-induced damage. The pulled-out particles trapped under the contact also abrade the ceramics, further increasing the severity of the microstructural damage.

With this mechanistic model, the lower resistance of SiC-nG to mild wear observed in Fig. 3 is explicable essentially in terms of its lower hardness, which is not compensated by a lower friction coefficient (i.e., self-lubrication). In this scenario, SiC-nG is less resistant than SiC-Ref to dislocation plasticity, and therefore the stress accumulation rate ($\dot{\sigma}_D$) increases resulting in a greater mild-wear rate and higher wear damage. The earlier mild-to-severe wear transition in SiC-nG is the result of the competition between various effects. In particular, $\sigma_D(t)$ is higher in SiC-nG than in SiC-Ref (because $\dot{\sigma}_D$ was higher and $\sigma_D(t) = \dot{\sigma}_D \cdot t$), which tends to

shorten the transition; D , however, is on average slightly smaller in SiC-nG than in SiC-Ref, which tends to delay the transition. Despite the $\sigma_D(t)$ effect predominating, with these opposing trends and given that q only plays a minor role (if any), the one order of magnitude difference in the wear-transition time indicates that the thin mat of graphite nanoparticles on the SiC grains also induced a much poorer grain cohesion, thus appreciably reducing K^{GB} . This is consistent with independent wear observations on SiC/Si₃N₄-graphite composites [12] and on SiC-BN composites [13]. Finally, the lower severe-wear rate of SiC-nG compared to SiC-Ref is due to the combination of (i) its higher toughness, which hinders the crack propagation and coalescence responsible for the grain pull-out, (ii) the lower hardness of the wear debris due to its lower SiC concentration, and (iii) the external lubrication imposed by the pull-out graphite nanoparticles, both of which reduce the abrasion by third bodies. This is also consistent with previous wear observations on SiC-BN composites. **Due to its lower severe-wear rate, it is expected that SiC-nG will eventually show lower damage than SiC-Ref for very prolonged sliding times**, a scenario that was not, however, observed here due to the insufficient sliding time of only 500 min.

The present results have some interesting implications for triboceramic science. Clearly, nano-graphite dispersion in the microstructure is detrimental to the mild-wear and early severe-wear resistances, but beneficial to the severe-wear resistance after prolonged sliding. Therefore, depending on how demanding are the conditions of the corresponding tribological application, this approach would or would not be justified. For example, the nano-graphite addition would be very useful if the LPS SiC ceramic is to operate under the typical scenario of abrasive wear, where severe wear with material removal occurs from the beginning. However, graphite nanodispersoids (no matter how they are obtained) are not recommendable in practice over other alternative candidates such as graphite or BN flakes. Indeed, the comparison with earlier wear

data on LPS SiC ceramics [13] (see Fig. 3) demonstrates that 10 vol.% addition of flaky micrometric BN particles produces essentially the same effects as the present addition of graphite nanodispersoids, but in the former case with greater improvement of the fracture toughness and with less tedious processing. This will also likely be the case for cost-effective flaky graphite [12] and for more expensive graphene nanoplatelets [19], which would thus also be preferable over graphite nanodispersoids. In any case, it does not seem to be a solution for the improvement of mild-wear resistance either. It is not clear whether or not the addition of carbon nanotubes will help in this latter objective because, while they have proven to act as grain “ligaments” under other mechanical deformation modes [20], this has yet to be shown under sliding wear, which needs to be investigated. Finally, a different type of microstructural design that is worth investigating is the “true” duplex microstructure with grains of the SiC matrix and of the self-lubrication phase. Whereas this microstructural architecture would be hard to prepare with graphite or BN (which are flaky) dispersoids, it perhaps could be achieved with additions of other harder ceramic phases with lower friction coefficients (Si_3N_4 , AlN, etc.).

5. Conclusions

We have introduced graphite nanodispersoids into the microstructure of a fine-grained LPS SiC ceramic fabricated by SPS, and investigated their effect on the lubricated sliding-wear behaviour. Based on the results and analyses, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Upon prolonged sliding contact, LPS SiC ceramics containing graphite nanodispersoids exhibit the same two-stage sliding-wear behavior as other polycrystalline ceramics, namely: an initial mild, deformation-controlled wear regime, followed by a transition to a subsequent severe, fracture-controlled wear regime.

2. The addition of graphite nanodispersoids is detrimental to the mild-wear resistance of LPS SiC by increasing its wear rate and decreasing the transition time to severe wear. This is because the introduction of softer graphite particles leads to a decrease in hardness, and their preferential location at grain boundaries/faces worsens the cohesion of the SiC grains.
3. The addition of graphite nanodispersoids is beneficial to the severe-wear resistance of LPS SiC by effectively decreasing its wear rate, and is ultimately expected to decrease the extent of the wear damage for very prolonged sliding times. This is because the graphite nanodispersoids lead to an increase in the fracture toughness, and also because graphite third bodies provide some external lubrication after grain pull-out.
4. In practical terms, graphite nanodispersoids offers no additional benefits over other self-lubricating phases with flaky morphology, such as the typical BN particles and most likely graphite particles too.

Acknowledgements This work was supported by the Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología (Government of Spain) and Feder Funds under Grant No. MAT 2010–16848 and MAT 2012–31090.

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Figure Captions

Fig. 1. Representative SEM micrographs of the fracture surface of the broken (A) SiC-Ref and (B) SiC-nG at moderate magnification. The insets show details of interest at higher magnification.

Fig. 2. Representative SEM micrographs of the polished surface of (A) SiC-Ref and (B) SiC-nG at moderate magnification, after plasma etching with CF_4+O_2 gas for 30 min. Some grain boundaries are over etched.

Fig 3. XRD pattern of SiC-nG. The phase identification is included (only representative peaks have been indexed). The inset shows the zone $25-32^\circ 2\theta$ in more detail (where signature peaks of $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ appear).

Fig. 4. Sliding-wear curves for SiC-Ref and SiC-nG. Points are the experimental data. The solid lines are the fits to the data in the mild and severe wear regimes, with the discontinuities in the lines indicating a wear regime transition. The dashed line is the sliding-wear curve measured earlier for an LPS SiC containing 10 vol.% flaky BN (taken from [13]), which has been included for the sake of comparison.

Fig. 5. Representative SEM micrographs of the wear scars (semi-diameters) at the end of the wear tests in (A) SiC-Ref and (B) SiC-nG at low magnification, together with higher-magnification SEM micrographs of the region marked within the worn surface. The semi-circular lines delimit the contact surface during the wear tests.

